

On some nano Δ -open set in nanotopological spaces

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Abstract: The object of the article work is define a new class of some nano sets, we study properties of nano Δ -open and semi nano Δ -open and we define the nano Δ -interior, nano Δ -closure, semi nano Δ -interior and semi nano Δ -closure of a set E_1 in a nano topological spaces.

Key words: n -open sets, ns -open sets, nano Δ -open sets, semi nano Δ -open sets.

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

In 2013 M. Lellis Thivagar et al. introduced the concept of nano topological spaces and weak form of nano sets, nano semi-open (or ns -open) sets and nano semi-closed (or ns -closed) sets.

After that many nano topologist paved their own pathway in nano spaces introducing new types of nano sets.

Through out this article, The elements of $\tau_R(X)$ are called nano-open sets (or n -open sets).

The complement of a n -open set is called n -closed. we signify a nano space by (U, \mathcal{N}) , where $\mathcal{N} = \tau_R(X)$. The nano-interior and nano-closure of a subset E_1 of U are denoted by $n-I(E_1)$ and $n-C(E_1)$.

2. On nano Δ -open and semi nano Δ -open sets

Definition 2.1. A subset E_1 of a nano space is called a

1. nano Δ -open $\iff E_1 = (Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1)$, where Z_1 and Z_2 are n -open subsets in U .
2. semi nano Δ -open $\iff E_1 = (Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1)$, where Z_1 and Z_2 are ns -open subsets in U .

The complements of the above mentioned sets are called their respective nano closed sets.

Definition 2.2. A subset E_1 of a nano space is called a

1. nano Δ -interior of E_1 is defined as $\cup\{D : D \subseteq E_1 \text{ and } D \text{ is nano } \Delta\text{-open}\}$.
2. nano Δ -closure of E_1 is defined as $\cap\{D : E_1 \subseteq D \text{ and } D \text{ is nano } \Delta\text{-closed}\}$.
3. semi nano Δ -interior of E_1 is defined as $\cup\{D : D \subseteq E_1 \text{ and } D \text{ is semi nano } \Delta\text{-open}\}$.

4. semi nano Δ -closure of E_1 is defined as $\cap\{D : E_1 \subseteq D \text{ and } D \text{ is semi nano } \Delta\text{-closed}\}$.

The nano Δ -interior, nano Δ -closure, semi nano Δ -interior and semi nano Δ -closure of a subset E_1 of U are indicated by $n-\Delta I(E_1)$, $n-\Delta C(E_1)$, $ns-\Delta I(E_1)$ and $ns-\Delta C(E_1)$ respectively.

Remark 2.1. *In a nano space, if E_1 is nano Δ -open set as moreover every nano semi-open set is semi nano Δ -open.*

But the converse implications are not true.

Example 2.1. *Let $U = \{100, 101, 102\}$ with $U/R = \{\{100\}, \{101, 102\}\}$ and $X = \{100\}$. Then $\mathcal{N} = \{\{100\}, \phi, U\}$ is a nano topology on U . Then $\{101\}$ is semi nano Δ -open but is neither nano Δ -open nor ns -open.*

Theorem 2.1. *If E_1 is a semi nano Δ -open $\implies \exists$ a nano Δ -open set $V_1 \ni V_1 \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(V_1)$.*

Proof.

If E_2 is semi nano Δ -open, there exist ns -open sets Z_1 and Z_2 such that $E_2 = (Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1)$. Now, Z_1 and Z_2 are ns -open sets, it follows that \exists n -open sets K_1 and K_2 in $U \ni K_1 \subseteq Z_1 \subseteq n-C(K_1)$ and $K_2 \subseteq Z_2 \subseteq n-C(K_2)$. This implies that $(R_1 - R_2) \cup (R_2 - R_1) \subseteq (Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1) \subseteq [n-C(R_1) - n-C(R_2)] \cup [n-C(R_2) - n-C(R_1)] \subseteq n-C(R_1 - R_2) \cup n-C(R_2 - R_1) = n-C[(R_1 - R_2) \cup (R_2 - R_1)]$.

Theorem 2.2. *If E_1 is n -open and E_2 is semi nano Δ -open in a nano space, then $E_1 \cap E_2$ is semi nano Δ -open in U .*

Proof.

Let $E_1 \cap E_2 = E_1 \cap [(Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1)]$ where Z_1 and Z_2 are ns -open in U .

$E_1 \cap [(Z_1 - Z_2) \cup (Z_2 - Z_1)] = [E_1 \cap (Z_1 - Z_2)] \cup [E_1 \cap (Z_2 - Z_1)] = [(E_1 \cap Z_1) - (E_1 \cap Z_2)] \cup [(E_1 \cap Z_2) - (E_1 \cap Z_1)]$ which is semi nano Δ -open (since $(E_1 \cap Z_2)$ and $(E_1 \cap Z_1)$ are ns -open).

Theorem 2.3. *A subset E_1 of a nano space is semi nano Δ -open $\iff E_1 \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$.*

Proof.

E_1 be a semi nano Δ -open subset of U . Then \exists a nano Δ -open set $G \ni G \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(G)$. But $G = n-\Delta I(G) \subseteq n-\Delta I(E_1)$ and so $n-C(G) \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$. Thus $E_1 \subseteq n-C(G) \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$. Now, suppose $E_1 \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$. Put $G = n-\Delta I(E_1)$. Thus G is nano Δ -open with $G \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$. Hence $G \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(G)$ and E_1 is semi nano Δ -open.

Theorem 2.4. *If $\{E_1\}_i : i \in K$ is a family of semi nano Δ -open subsets, then $\bigcup_{i \in K} \{E_1\}_i$ is semi nano Δ -open.*

Proof.

For each $i \in K$, \exists a semi nano Δ -open set G_i such that $G_i \subseteq \{E_1\}_i \subseteq n-C(G_i)$. Now $\bigcup_{i \in E_1} \{E_1\}_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in K} \{E_1\}_i \subseteq \bigcup_{i \in K} n-C(G_i) \subseteq n-C(\bigcup_{i \in K} G_i)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in K} \{E_1\}_i$ is semi nano Δ -open.

Theorem 2.5. *Let E_1 be a subset of a nano space. Then $ns-\Delta I(E_1) = E_1 \cap n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$.*

Proof.

Let $E_1 \cap n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1)) \subseteq n-C[n-\Delta I(E_1 \cap n-I(E_1))] \subseteq n-C[n-\Delta I(E_1 \cap n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1)))]$. Thus $E_1 \cap n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$ is semi nano Δ -open set contained in E_1 . Hence $E_1 \cap n-C(\Delta I(E_1)) \subseteq ns-\Delta I(E_1)$.

On the other hand, since $ns-\Delta I(E_1)$ is a semi nano Δ -open set, we have $ns-\Delta I(E_1) \subseteq n-C(n-\Delta I(ns-\Delta I(E_1))) \subseteq n-C(ns-\Delta I(E_1))$. Hence $ns-\Delta I(E_1) = E_1 \cap n-C(n-\Delta I(E_1))$.

Theorem 2.6. *Let (V, \mathcal{N}) be a subspace of a space (U, \mathcal{N}) and let $E_1 \subseteq V$. If E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in U , then E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in V .*

Proof.

Let E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in U , there exist a nano Δ -open set K in U such that $K \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(K)$. Then $K = K \cap V \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C(K) \cap V = n-C_V(K)$. Thus E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in V .

Theorem 2.7. *Let V be a nano Δ -open set in a space (U, \mathcal{N}) . If $E_1 \subseteq V$ and E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in V , then E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in U .*

Proof.

Let E_1 be semi nano Δ -open in V . Then \exists a nano Δ -open subset K of $(V, \mathcal{N}) \ni K \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C_V(K)$. Since V is nano Δ -open in U , therefore, K is nano Δ -open in U and $K \subseteq E_1 \subseteq n-C_V(K) \subseteq n-C(K)$. Hence E_1 is semi nano Δ -open in U .

Theorem 2.8. *A subset E_1 of a space (U, \mathcal{N}) is semi nano Δ -closed $\iff n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1)) \subseteq E_1$.*

Proof.

Obvious.

Theorem 2.9. *If E_1 is a subspace of a space (U, \mathcal{N}) , then $ns-\Delta C(E_1) = E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1))$.*

Proof.

Let $n-I[n-\Delta C(E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1)))] \subseteq n-I[n-\Delta C(E_1 \cup n-C(E_1))] = n-I[n-\Delta C(E_1)] \subseteq E_1 \cup n-I[n-\Delta C(E_1)]$. Thus by Theorem 2.8 is $E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1))$ is a semi nano Δ -closed set containing E_1 and so $ns-\Delta C(E_1) \subseteq E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1))$.

On the other hand, since $ns-\Delta C(E_1)$ is semi nano Δ -closed, therefore,

$$n-I[n-\Delta C(ns-\Delta C(E_1)) \subseteq ns-\Delta C(E_1)].$$

Hence $n-I[n-\Delta C(E_1)] \subseteq n-I[n-\Delta C(ns-\Delta C(E_1))] \subseteq ns-\Delta C(E_1)$ and consequently $E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1)) \subseteq ns-\Delta C(E_1)$. Thus $ns-\Delta C(E_1) = E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1))$.

Theorem 2.10. *Let E_1 is a subset of (U, \mathcal{N}) . Then $ns-\Delta C(E_1) \subseteq ns-C(E_1) \cap n-\Delta C(E_1)$*

Proof.

$$\text{Let } ns-\Delta C(E_1) = E_1 \cup n-I(n-\Delta C(E_1)) \subseteq n-I(n-C(E_1)) = ns-C(E_1).$$

$$\text{Also, } ns-\Delta C(E_1) \subseteq E_1 \cup n-\Delta C(E_1) = n-\Delta C(E_1). \text{ Therefore, } ns-\Delta C(E_1) \subseteq ns-C(E_1) \cap n-\Delta C(E_1).$$

Theorem 2.11. *If K is n -closed and M is semi nano Δ -closed in a space (U, \mathcal{N}) , then $K \cup M$ is semi nano Δ -closed.*

Proof.

Let $(U - K)$ is n -open and $(U - M)$ is semi nano Δ -open. Then by Theorem 2.2 $(U - K) \cap (U - M)$ is semi nano Δ -open. That is $U - (K \cup M)$ is semi nano Δ -open. Hence $K \cup M$ is semi nano Δ -closed.

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